

Extent of Utilization of Artificial Intelligence for Improving the Teaching of Business Education among University Business Educators in South-South, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The study ascertained the extent of utilization of artificial intelligence (AI) for improving the teaching of business education among university business educators in South-South, Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study and one null hypothesis was tested. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised 202 university business educators in South-South, Nigeria. The instrument for data collection was a 15-item questionnaire. The instrument was validated by three experts. Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability of the instrument and obtained an overall coefficient value of 0.89. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that AI were rarely utilized by university business educators, while male business educators had higher mean rating than their female counterparts on the extent they utilize AI for improving the teaching of business education programme in South-South, Nigeria. The findings revealed that male and female university business educators do not significantly differ in their mean responses on the extent they utilized AI for improving the teaching of business education programme in in South-South, Nigeria. The study concluded that AI listed in the study was not widely utilized by university business educators for improving the teaching of business education programme in South-South, Nigeria. It was recommended among others that, university management should collaborate with experts in ICT and education to develop 21st-century learners centred course materials with interactive elements and immediate feedback that can further strengthen the use of AI for educational purposes.

Keywords: Utilization, Artificial Intelligence, Business Education, University, Business Educators

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative force across various sectors, offering innovative solutions to complex problems. In the realm of education, AI holds the potential to revolutionize traditional teaching methods and streamline research processes. Artificial Intelligence refers to the development of computer systems capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence. AI is considered a key example of Education Revolution 5.1 products. Education Revolution 5.1, or the “Fifth Industrial Revolution in Education,” emphasizes personalized and human-centric learning experiences enhanced by technology. AI plays a crucial role in this revolution by enabling adaptive learning platforms, personalized tutoring systems, and tools for content creation and analysis, ultimately aiming to improve educational outcomes and efficiency (Eleyyan, 2021). Raji and Amadi (2023) defined AI as programmes designed with human like intelligence and structured in the forms of computers, robots, or other machine to aid in the provision of any kind of service or tasks to improve the social economic and political development

of the society. Artificial Intelligence is an application, collections of systems, packages and programme designed into digital computers or computer-controlled robots to carry out assignments and tasks with human-like intelligence (Amadi-Iwai, Ubulom and Okiridu, 2024; Thomas, Gambari, Sobowale and Shehu, 2021).

Currently, artificial intelligence is being utilized in education to foster personalized, automation of teaching administrative automation, data analysis and so on. AI has continued to develop new ways of application in education which include; customized/personalized learning, smarter content, improved learning effectiveness and efficiency in administration (Onah, Onyebuchi, Eke and Adayi, 2020). AI promotes personalised productive learning behaviour, such as self-regulation, self-monitoring and self-explanation as it provides learning activities at the learners' pace and with the most appropriate content, timely guidance, feedback and explanations (Fernandez, Fernandez and Aburto, 2019). Intelligent Tutoring Systems provide personalised learning to learners, automatic correction of certain kinds of schoolwork, which enables lecturers to have time for other tasks, help lecturers adjust their courses to some extent, provide ongoing feedback on students' assessment. AI is being used, for instance, by MOOC platforms and Coursera to alert instructors when a large number of students provide an inaccurate response to a topic (Karsenti, 2019).

AI software and web browsers can be used to predict citation impact, automate the extraction of references from PDF articles, organize and share research questions in a research. Thus, AI frees the researcher's time that would have been used for sorting and arranging of reference materials. Examples of such software and web browsers are Mendeley, Scopus, and EndNote. AI integrates Grammarly Premium to automate proofreading, identify and correct errors in research writing while also preventing plagiarism; this will enable the researcher to focus on the content being written rather than the grammatical or spelling errors. Education develops mind and expands knowledge bases and learning process involves a person carrying out a particular action within a specific situation, and then recognizing the effect of that action (Thomas et-al., 2021). Therefore, AI is essential to both learners and lecturers. AI is already being used in universities. For instance, Deakin University in Australia already applied IBM's supercomputer Watson as an emerging form of artificial intelligence and a solution to provide students with advice (Fahimirad and Kotamjani, 2018). This innovation significantly made efficient modifications to the quality of services rendered and time spent teaching students within a university. Most Nigerian universities also make use of Artificial Intelligence based applications to detect plagiarism in students' work (Karsenti, 2019). For example, turn-it-in can recognize degrees of plagiarism in students' works when they "turn it in" (Karsenti, 2019). It shows the parts that are likely to have been plagiarised, the potential sources, and the percentages of the potential sources that have been plagiarized by the university business educators. Business educators that are unable to embrace and utilize the application of AI in business education in Nigeria could lead to several negative impacts, including potential job displacement, over-reliance on technology, and ethical concerns. While AI offers benefits like personalized learning, it also raises issues of data privacy, reduced human interaction, and the reinforcement of biases in training data.

The government of Nigeria has taken steps to promote partnerships and stakeholder engagement towards the advancement of AI in the country, this is obvious in the formation of a National Agency for Research in Robotics and Artificial Intelligence (NARRAI) in 2018. However, based on available information, awareness of AI and robotics, including NARRAI (which is not explicitly mentioned in the search results but is related to the field), was likely limited, especially among the general public. According to the Minister of Science and Technology, Dr. Ogbonnaya Onu, the

agency will coordinate and control all researches relating to AI and robotics. Ladeinde (2019) added that the agency will collaborate with international research bodies, work with tertiary institutions and promote Nigeria's ability to leverage AI technologies for economic growth. Similarly, the then Minister of Communications Adebayo Shittu in March 2018 noted that NARRAI will work with international bodies to enhance the advancement of AI in Nigeria, support AI stakeholders and engage in activities to explore the utilization of AI in Nigeria.

A university business educator is a person who lectures as an occupation in a university business education programme. University is a tertiary institution in Nigeria that saddled with the responsibility of training graduates to obtain degree certificates in various disciplines. In education, the role of the business educators is that of a guide, mentor, facilitator, academic supervisor and instrument to ensure comprehensive learning. The utilization of AI in education depends on the availability and accessibility of the AI technologies, enabling environment, skills and knowledge on how to use the AI technologies. This was emphasized by Eze, Chinedu-Eze, Okike and Bello (2020) who noted that the successful implementation of educational innovations depends largely on the skills and knowledge of the lecturers. University business educator as a facilitator, guides the learner to play an active role to get to his or her understanding of the content (Masaazi, 2015). University business educator who are competent in using artificial intelligence tools can experience improved job performance in various aspects. These improvements may include enhanced instructional delivery, better student engagement, more personalized learning experiences, and increased efficiency in administrative tasks. This is similar to Amadi-Iwai et-al. (2024) who uphold that the use of artificial intelligence can greatly impact teaching and learning through effective information symmetry. Artificial Intelligence accelerates tasks and expands human expertise with speed and accuracy thereby helping institutions push efficiencies within various stakeholder to manage operational costs and improving performance as well as achieving education goals (Amadi-Iwai et-al., 2024). Amadi-Iwai et-al. (2024) stated that to utilize artificial intelligence effectively, business educators and institutions will need to increase their investments in data, skills and digital workflows.

Business educators in the university can leverage AI to; automate administrative tasks, provide feedback, enhance content delivery, and facilitate collaboration. For instance, AI can help educators grade assignments, monitor students' progress, customize curriculum, and identify learning gaps. AI can also allow educators to generate responses, create more engaging and interactive lessons, using tools like ChatGPT to simulate, and gamify. More importantly, AI can enable educators to collaborate with peers and experts across the world, sharing best practices and resources. AI has been integrated into education, in the form of intelligent books, smart devices, web browsers, education applications, learning platforms and tutoring systems. With the utilization of Artificial Intelligence in teaching and learning, learners will have access to an unprecedented amount of authentic relevant information to enable them to manage their learning activities as well as explore relevant learning materials and become inquisitive, rather than solely passive recipients of knowledge and information from only the lecturer. Thus, enhancing self-learning and active participation in the learning process.

Despite, the benefits of utilizing AI to improve the quality and effectiveness of teaching and learning process, assessment and professional development of lecturers, existing literature has shown contradiction in the utilization of modern technologies by lecturers. Research evidence has shown a low degree of modern technologies for education usage among lecturers (Onah et-al., 2020) while studies by Ukeh and Anih (2024) revealed that lecturers often utilized modern technologies in their

tasks. Yushau and Nannim (2020) who revealed that lecturers' extent of utilization of ICT facilities was low. Thomas and Gambari (2021) reported there is no significant difference in the extent of ICT usage by male and female teachers. Eze et-al. (2020) stated that male lecturers slightly had higher mean rating than their female counterparts on the extent of utilization of ICT teaching facilities. Today's technology-driven economy demands business educators to be digital compliance. Hence the study sought to ascertain the extent of utilization of artificial intelligence for improving the teaching of business education among university business educators in South- South, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

In this digital age, Artificial Intelligence plays a significant role in the educational success such as in business education programme where lecturers and learners achieve benefit of offering them new innovative ways of teaching and learning, assessment, acquiring skills, communicating, sharing, creating, grading, analyzing and interacting with learning materials. AI when effectively integrated and utilized optimally in the teaching and learning process will enhance the development of digital literacy and informed learners in the digital age. The work of a business educator is demanding, especially in Nigerian institutions with insufficient technologies and large class size with learners of different learning abilities. AI devices, applications and software can be used by business educators as very effective supporting tools (Eze et-al., 2020). Owing to the numerous benefits associated with the utilization of AI in education, this study ascertained the extent of utilization of artificial intelligence for improving the teaching of business education among university business educators in South- South, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to ascertain the extent of utilization of artificial intelligence for improving the teaching of business education among university business educators in South-South, Nigeria. Specifically, the study ascertained:

1. University business educators' extent of utilizing Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme.
2. The difference between male and female business educators' extent of utilizing Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme?

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent do university business educators utilize Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme in South-South, Nigeria?
2. To what extent is the difference between male and female business educators utilize Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme in South- South, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Male and female university business educators do not significantly differ in their mean responses on the extent they utilize Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme in in South-South, Nigeria.

Method

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised 202 university business educators owned by government in South-South, Nigeria. The entire population was used for the study because of its manageable population size, hence, the study adopted census survey. A

15 items structured questionnaire was used for data collected. The structured questionnaire was validated by three experts-two in business education and one in measurement and evaluation all from Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Their comments enhanced the content validity of the instrument. To establish the internal consistency of the instrument, a pilot test was conducted. Data collected were analyzed using Cronbach Alpha to determine the internal consistency. Reliability coefficients value of 0.89 was obtained. Out of the 202 copies of the questionnaire distributed to the respondents in their institutions through direct approach facilitated a response rate of 193 copies (representing 96 percent) with an attrition rate of nine copies (representing 4 percent) and used for data analysis. Data collected regarding the research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation while t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. In order to determine the extent of utilization of artificial intelligence for improving the teaching of business education among university business educators in South-South, Nigeria, a decision rule based on real limit of numbers was used such that ratings between 3.50-4.00 were regarded as highly utilized, items with mean ratings of 2.50-3.49 were considered as utilized; items with mean ratings of 1.50-2.49 were considered as rarely utilized. Furthermore, items with mean ratings of 1.00-1.49 were considered not utilized respectively. In testing the null hypotheses, where the calculated p-value is less than the stipulated level of significance (0.05), it meant that there was a significant difference and the null hypothesis was rejected. Conversely, where the calculated p-value is greater than or equal to the stipulated level of significance (0.05), it meant that there was no significant difference and the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Results

Research Question 1:

To what extent do university business educators utilize Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme in South-South, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean ratings of university business educators utilize Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme in South-South, Nigeria. N =193

S/N Utilize Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
1. Smart board to promote class discussions and improve students' experiences and presentation skills	2.60	0.56	Utilized
2. AI learning platforms such as goggle classroom to enhance lecturers and learners' interaction	2.40	0.63	Rarely Utilized
3. AI software such as Turn-it-in to assess, provide feedback to students and ascertain their level of plagiarism	2.70	0.54	Utilized
4. AI learning platform like Netex learning to create customized students learning materials and incorporate interactive elements such as audio, video and self-assessment into the learning material	2.69	0.53	Utilized
5. Robots to provide customized answers in response to learners' messages, grade their performance, and provide tips on what area learners need to improve	1.24	0.71	Not Utilized
6. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) for immediate manipulation and computation of statistical analysis and mathematical calculations	3.20	0.51	Utilized
7. Google scholar to quickly see the main journals, disciplines and authors that publish in my area of interest	3.40	0.45	Utilized
8. Automated facial recognition like biometric face scanning surveillance to automate attendance roll marking in class and during examination	2.35	0.65	Rarely Utilized
9. Research gate for collaboration with colleagues and peers of similar interest in research	3.24	0.49	Utilized
10. EndNote to automate the collection and curation of research materials and formatting of bibliographies	2.20	0.68	Rarely Utilized
11. Scopus a source neutral abstract and citation database, to generate precise citation search results and automatically create and update my research profile	2.45	0.62	Rarely Utilized
12. Mendeley to predict citation impact, automate extraction of metadata from PDF articles, organise and share research questions	2.36	0.65	Rarely Utilized
13. Grammarly Premium to automate proofreading identify and correct errors in my writing while preventing plagiarism	2.35	0.66	Rarely Utilized
14. Intelligent Essay Assessor an internet-based tool to automatically evaluate the meaning of the text, grammar, style, and the mechanics of my students' text structure	2.36	0.65	Rarely Utilized
15. GradeCam to read students' numeric handwriting, automatically score the answer based on the answer key provided	1.44	0.69	Not Utilized
Cluster Mean	2.47		Rarely Utilized

Data in Table 1 show that six out of the 15 items listed have mean ratings of 2.60 to 3.40 indicate that Artificial Intelligence are utilized for improving the teaching of business education programme. Seven items have mean ratings from 2.20 to 2.45 are rated as rarely utilized, while the remaining two items as not utilized and have mean ratings of 1.24 and 1.44. The standard deviation of 0.45 to 0.71 showed that respondents are not wide apart in their mean ratings which indicate homogeneity. The cluster mean score of 2.47 indicates that university business educators rarely utilize Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme in South-South, Nigeria.

Research Question 2:

To what extent is the difference between male and female business educators utilize Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme in South-South, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the difference between male and female business educators’ extent utilization of Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme in South-South, Nigeria

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	Mean Difference
Male	78	49.46	17.52	3.92
Female	115	45.54	13.71	

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of male and female university business educators utilize Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme. From the table, the mean and standard deviation of male business educators are $\bar{X} = 49.46$ with $SD = 17.52$ while the mean and standard deviation of female business educators are $\bar{X} = 45.54$ with $SD = 13.71$ with a mean difference of 3.92 in favour of male business educators. This shows that male business educators had higher mean rating than their female counterparts on the extent they utilize Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme in South-South, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 1:

Male and female university business educators do not significantly differ in their mean responses on the extent they utilize Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme in in South-South, Nigeria.

Table 3: Summary of t-test analysis on the mean responses of male and female university business educators on the extent they utilize Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme in in South-South, Nigeria.

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-cal.	p-value	Decision
Male	78	49.46	17.15	191	2.930	.065	Not Significant
Female	115	45.54	13.71				

NS: Not Significant at 0.05 (p>0.05)

Table 3 shows that mean score of university male business educators ($X=49.46$, $SD=17.15$) is significantly greater than that of university male business educators ($X=13.71$, $SD=13.71$), P -value of .065. The P -value is greater than the level of significance, hence hypothesis one was not rejected. This means that male and female university business educators do not significantly differ in their

mean responses on the extent they utilized Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme in in South-South, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Findings of first research question revealed that Artificial Intelligence were rarely utilize by university business educators for improving the teaching of business education programme in South-South, Nigeria. This finding is in line with Yushau and Nannim (2020) who revealed that lecturers' extent of utilisation of ICT facilities was low. Onah, Onyebuchi, Eke and Adayi (2020) noted university business educators has shown a low degree of modern technologies for education. The finding of the study disagrees with that of Ukeh and Anih (2024) who revealed that lecturers often utilised modern technologies in their tasks. This implies that the mean business educators could not utilized Artificial Intelligence to expectation for improving the teaching of business education programme in in South-South, Nigeria. It shows that benefit of using AI improve the quality and effectiveness of teaching and learning process, assessment and professional development of lecturers were not achieved.

The findings of the study revealed that male and female university business educators do not significantly differ in their mean responses on the extent they utilized Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme in in South-South, Nigeria. These findings agree with Thomas and Gambari (2021) who reported there is no significant difference in the extent of ICT usage by male and female teachers.

The findings of second research question revealed that male business educators had higher mean rating than their female counterparts on the extent they utilize Artificial Intelligence for improving the teaching of business education programme in South-South, Nigeria. The finding disagrees with Eze, Chinedu-Eze, Okike and Bello (2020) who stated that male lecturers slightly had higher mean rating than their female counterparts on the extent of utilisation of ICT teaching facilities.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that most of the Artificial Intelligence listed in the study was not widely used by university business educators for improving the teaching of business education programme in South-South, Nigeria. This suggests a potential gap in the utilization of Artificial Intelligence tools in the teaching of business education programme and its academic environment. Further efforts and initiatives may be needed to promote the effective implementation of artificial intelligence technologies to enhance teaching and research practices in these institutions. Meanwhile, the incorporation of AI tools in teaching and research represents a significant paradigm shift in higher education. Business educators, embracing the important of AI, are leveraging these tools to enhance the learning experience and streamline research processes. As technology continues to evolve, ongoing research and collaboration will be crucial to maximizing the benefits of AI in education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. University business educators rarely utilized AI, therefore, university management should regularly organise hands-on and professional training programmes and retreat for lecturers to teach and effectively use AI for teaching.
2. University management should collaborate with experts in ICT and education to develop 21st-century learners centred course materials with interactive elements and immediate feedback that can further strengthen the use of AI for educational purposes.

3. Male and female business educators in the University and other tertiary institutions should be properly trained on the use of AI to enhance their academic performance.
4. Male and female business educators in the University could perform equally well if enabling environment with adequate infrastructure are provided, therefore, management of university business education programme in South-South, Nigeria should provide conducive and enabling environment to both male and female lecturers for them to effectively use AI for education.

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